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Introduction

Emotions are pleasant or unpleasant experiences that arise from a person's thoughts and feelings about an event, related to his needs and interests. And many people today are driven by emotions. The violation is causing many problems. And so far, several solutions to these problems have been found, and this research is ongoing. At this point, we may have a question. WHO CAN CORRECT EMOTIONAL DISORDERS? We all know that emotion is a field related to human emotions, and the problems in it are caused by emotions, and of course, the solution to this problem is also related to psychology. Because one of the important tasks of psychology is to control a person through his emotions. Psychologists can do the same. Psychologists have divided the treatment period into types according to age. And through this article, we will explore and discuss emotional disorders in kindergarten-age children and ways to correct them.

PSYCHOCORRECTION OF EMOTIONAL DISORDERS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the psychology of preschool children and the various emotional disorders that occur in this condition. There was also talk of their solutions. You can also see a lot of ideas about the demands of the 21st century and the style-psychology that can open many closed doors without a key. But the main goal is to find a psychological solution to emotional disorders.

Significant changes are beginning to take place in the psychological and emotional development of children of kindergarten age. Because from this period the child's independent activity begins to grow externally. Almost all emotional processes of a child of kindergarten age develop rapidly. As a result, the child gradually becomes acquainted with the environment, which leads to many changes in the child's thinking. At the age of kindergarten, along with the development of certain psychological processes, they also begin to create personal and personal qualities

Literature review

There are so many types it is hard to say. Not understanding the connection can cause stress for the child. Stress, on the other hand, leads to a breakdown in the emotional state of the child. The results of the theoretical work show that there are several effective ways to solve this problem, one of which is to explain it through games that children like. This is

one of the best ways to keep a child safe. Kindergarten-age children can learn about their surroundings only through actions. Adults around children can learn a lot of things that belong to their lives, which they still do not have the strength and intelligence to do, only during play activities. Through play, they know and remember things and events that occur in life. Play is not only a means of knowing and understanding things around them but also a powerful educational tool should be taught.

Kindergarten psychology is very sensitive and changeable. Based on the child's interests, Professor E.A. Arkin divides kindergarten games into approximate classification groups.

1. Games aimed at improving certain psychological processes in children:

- A) games that improve the sensory organs;
- B) movement (sports games);
- C) aesthetic games;

2. Technical games;

- A) industrial games;
- B) agricultural games;
- C) career-related games;
- D) construction games;

3. Life and socio-political games;

- A) Family life games
- B) kindergarten school games;
- C) social games;
- D) socio-political games;

4. Military games.

- A) Red Army game;
- B) sailor game;
- C) war game;

5. Dramatic games

- A) theatrical performance;
- B) a movie game;
- C) circus game.

It is well known that didactic games (such as drawing different shapes from

lottery cubes, numbers, mosaics, checkers, and riddles) help in many ways to successfully conduct a special program in kindergarten.

Results

Kindergarten children play games that are mostly plot and role-playing, and they like these games. In role-playing games, children reflect on their surroundings.

In conclusion, the play activities of kindergarten children of different ages help to reflect and develop all their emotional states. That is, it develops psychological processes, mental abilities, personal-psychological qualities, character traits.

We better and more comprehensively understand things and events in the external environment not only through perception but also through perception. From the perception of a certain thing, children rely not on a single sign of that thing, but on several signs. Later, when they encounter the same thing for the second time, they can distinguish it from other similar things based on the signs they already know. When children perceive different things around them, they can only see these big signs and understand what they see. However, due to their lack of life experience, children do not understand the most important and general features related to the content of things.

Kindergarten children can tell the difference between the shapes of similar things. But when we show young kindergarten children abstract geometric shapes or pictures of them, they try to understand these shapes by relating them to specific things they know. For example, they call a circle a car balloon, a rectangle a window, and a triangle an object.

This deficiency in children's perception is evident in their ability to understand different images. In general, children of kindergarten age are very interested in seeing different pictures. But they are completely indifferent to the state and spatial relationship of the things depicted in the picture. That's why small groups of children often look at different pictures upside down and enjoy them. But later on, it can cause negative emotional states in the child.

Conclusion

In short, emotions and feelings are the leading activities in preschool. Preschoolers' emotions are intensely developed through play. Play is not only a

leading activity for preschoolers but also a variety of experiences. Depending on the situation, a child's feelings and emotions can be both positive (love, joy) and negative (anger, hatred). Positive experiences are created when a child can meet their needs. If the child is not able to meet his needs in the created situation, negative emotional experiences will arise. One of the main requirements of psychological preparation for school is emotional preparation. This preparation requires not only the joy of waiting for school to begin but also the development of higher emotions, the formation of the emotional characteristics of the child's personality.

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